

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT PRACTICES IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research article is to evaluate the Continuous Assessment Practices towards the student rendered by the Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College in Perambalur. The researcher conducted a literature search on College of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College interviewing of its 312 students (222 Males and 90 Females) and thoroughly scrutinized how it continuous Assessment impact among student academic point of view. The study also focused on various factors that determine the Continuous Assessment Practices like Students' Behaviour, Attendance, Performance, Involvement and Internal Assessment Marks. Analysis was made by using various tools like Percentage Analysis and Chi square. The result showed that there was a significant relationship between the variable of Continuous Assessment Practices and the students have satisfaction of the colleges.

Key Words: Education, Continuous Assessment Practice, Continuous Assessment methods, Assignment and Attendance, Assessment for Learning.

Introduction:

Continuous Assessment Practices introduced 2018 year in the college. College is being following on instructions to Continuous Assessment Practices. Continuous Assessment Practices is a classroom strategy of implemented by college teachers to ascertain the knowledge, skills and understanding attained by students at a particular point in time. Teachers doing assessments in a variety of ways in order to observe multiple tasks and information about what students know understand and can do. The Continuous assessment is a method of evaluation carried out periodically or at a predetermined interval of the college's year. It is aimed at finding out how much students have are learning in a subject matter. It is a consistence monitoring of students' progress in college.

The continuous assessment practice regular system requires the assessment of the change in different student's education activities, in terms of cognitive effective and domains. The students are evaluated from one stage to the other through tests, assignments, projects and college activities. At the end of the terms or session, the tests are used for determining the performance of the students in a particular subject. College using examinations, educators are expressing an increased interest in continuous assessments.

Components of Continuous Assessment:

The Continuous Assessment for this course will be based on Components.

- Daily Class time of the Attendance Records.
- Three modes of Assignments.
- Written Assignment will helpful for your Writing Practices improve University Exams.
- Seminar Assignment and help to Change on your Stage Fear.
- A Presentation Assignment Power Point Presentation Assignment will improve your Creative Thinking.
- There Slip Test use Preparing University Exam, and helpful for Time Management.
- Assessments I and II, Model Exam is conducting to evaluation of student subject knowledge.

Continuous assessment is regular assessment of the learning performance related to a course module and that is separate from examinations, and accompanied by regular feedback. Continuous assessment can take various forms, depending on the final objectives and competencies.

Literature Reviews:

Holmes (2015), in the current paper, all forms of assessment during the course will be referred to as 'Intermediate assessment' synonyms are 'frequent' or 'continuous' assessment, see. Intermediate assessment may influence three different types of student outcomes, namely active, cognitive or behavioral outcomes. Some examples of these outcomes are student perceptions of their learning student engagement student studying behavior and student grades.

Belter (2013), Assessment is a powerful force in education. Posit that practice testing is an effective studying technique, next to distributed practice (the process of studying constantly throughout a study period instead of cramming). Since these two processes enhance student learning in self-study, it stands to reason that distributed assessments should be an integral part of a course, encompassing different assessment moments

during the course instead of just a internal examination. In higher education, these assessments during the course often take various forms.

Watkins (2007), Nature of continuous assessment in the context of international perspectives concerning teacher assessments is organized under the following subtopics continuous assessment and curriculum-based assessments explains, in countries that have evidently designed national curriculum, continuing, influential assessment is typically based on aim and attached directly to the aims for the curriculum designed for all the students. National strategies for assessment may define what needs to be assessed and how it is to be assessed. Inside the countries using this method, main features is that developing and applying assessment is mostly the duty of conventional schools and class teachers. This is according to the purpose of such assessment for notifying decisions about next steps in an individual student’s learning.

Research Methodology:

Respondents were asked to give on different aspects of Continuous Assessment towards the Students provided by Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College and the questionnaire was rated with the aid of four liker scaled subjects ranging between one and four 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Agree, 4=Strongly Agree.

Statement of Problem:

In order to reach the set objectives and through the availability of literatures the researcher stated the problems as Continuous Assessment Practices towards Students of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College in Perambalur.

Objectives of the Study:

- To Study used to make Awareness towards Continuous Assessment Practices among Students.
- To analyze the role of Continuous Assessment Practices in improving Students Internal Marks in Academic Results.

Limitation of the Study:

- Individual Opinion of the Student is different from each other so we can’t Easily Derive the Conclusion.
- It is Time Consuming Process.
- For Study on Engineering Students Only.
- The Student Individual Behavior One of Factor will affect the Study.

Scope of Study:

- The Continuous Assessment Practice helpful for Student to Update Knowledge.
- To Analyzes Student Performance Appraisal.
- The Methodology helpful for the Student who Concentrate on the Study.
- Evaluate the Knowledge Level of the Students.
- The Continuous Assessment Practice helpful for the Students to keep Time Management in Academic Tasks.
- The Continuous Assessment Practice will helpful for the Staff to Cover the Syllabus in Limited Period.

Data Collection Method:

A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. It accounts for primary Data. Primary source of data were collected from students through structured interview by way.

Sampling Techniques and Size:

Sampling is a technique or method of selection of samples. The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves sampling method is used. The study has taken (222 Male and 90 Female) samples from students of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College in Perambalur.

Tools Used:

The primary data were analyzed with the help of percentage.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The required data has been collected by way of a Questionnaire and it has been analyzed and interpreted with the help of tables with relevant descriptions. Appropriate treatment has been done to the raw data and logical conclusions were drawn based on the findings.

Table 1: Age Wise Classification

S.No	Age Wise	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	18 Age	17	5
2	19 Age	55	18
3	20 Age	123	39
4	21 Age	62	20
5	Above 22 Age	55	18
Total		312	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is observed that age, 5 % of the respondents are 18 years age, 18 % of the respondents are 19 years age, 39 % of the respondents are 20 years age, 20 % of the respondents are 21 years age, and 18 % of the respondents Above 22 years age.

Table 2: Gender Wise Classification

S.No	Gender Wise	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Male	222	71
2	Female	90	29
Total		312	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is observed that Genders, Highest 71 % of the respondents are Male Genders and 29 % of the respondents are Female Genders.

Table 3: Like Continuous Assessment Practice

S.No	Like Continuous Assessment Practice	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	142	46
2	Neutral	52	17
3	No	38	12
4	Sometimes	70	22
5	Never	10	3
Total		312	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is observed that likes, 46 % of respondents are yes like, 17 % of respondents are Neutral like, 12 % of respondents are No like, 22 % of respondents are Sometimes like, and 3 % of respondents are never like.

Table 4: Understand by Continuous Assessment

S.No	Understand by Continuous Assessment	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Learning Process	82	26
2	Teaching Method	60	19
3	Neutral	48	15
4	Maintain The Interest on the Subject	55	18
5	None of These	67	22
Total		312	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is observed that Understand by Continuous Assessment, 26 % of respondents are Learning Process Understand by Continuous Assessment, 19 % of respondents are Teaching Methods Understand by Continuous Assessment, 15 % of respondents are Neutral Understand by Continuous Assessment, 18 % of respondents are Maintain the interest on the subject Understand by Continuous Assessment, and 22 % of respondents are None of these Understand by Continuous Assessment.

Table 5: Best Continuous Assessment Practices

S.No	Best Continuous Assessment Practices	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Attendance	77	25
2	3 Modes of Assignment	100	32
3	Slip Test	70	22
4	None of the Above	35	11
5	SIM Material	30	10
Total		312	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is observed that Best Continuous Assessment Practices, 25 % of respondents are Attendance Best Continuous Assessment Practices, 32 % of respondents are 3 Modes of Assignment Best Continuous Assessment Practices, 22 % of respondents are Slip Test Best Continuous Assessment Practices, 11

% of respondents are None of the above Best Continuous Assessment Practices, and 10 % of respondents are SIM Material Best Continuous Assessment Practices.

Correlation:

Table 6: Current Continuous Assessment Practices and One of the Best Continuous Assessment Practices

Current Continuous Assessment Practices (X)	15	148	90	32	27	312
One of the Best Continuous Assessment Practices (Y)	77	100	70	35	30	312

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
15	77	225	5929	1155
148	100	21904	10000	14800
90	70	8100	4900	6300
32	35	1024	1225	1120
27	30	729	900	810
312	312	31982	22954	24185

$\sum X=312, \sum Y=312, \sum X^2=31982, \sum Y^2=22954, \sum XY=24185, n=5$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}}$$

Answer = 0.714

Inference:

There is high Positive Correlation between Current Continuous Assessment Practices (X) and one of the Best Continuous Assessment Practices (Y).

Chi-Square Analysis:

To Compare the Continuous Assessment Practices Understanding and Improving your Performance Position by using Chi-Square test

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relation between the Understand by Continuous Assessment.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significant relation between the Continuous Assessment Practices will be improving your Performance.

Level of Significance $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7: Cross Tabulation for Continuous Assessment Practices Understanding and Improving Your Performance

Improving Your Performance	Learning Process	Teaching Method	Neutral	Maintain the Interest on the Subject	None of These	Row Total
High Satisfaction	15	7	5	8	5	40
Satisfaction	50	37	25	20	38	170
Neutral	10	10	15	20	12	67
Dissatisfaction	2	3	3	5	7	20
High Dissatisfaction	3	2	2	0	8	15
Column Total	80	59	50	53	70	312

O _i	E _i	O _i -E _i	O _i -E _i ²	O _i -E _i ² /E _i
15	10.25641	4.7435897	22.501644	2.1939103
7	7.5641026	-0.5641026	0.3182117	0.0420687
5	6.4102564	-1.4102564	1.9888231	0.3102564
8	6.7948718	1.2051282	1.452334	0.2137397
5	8.974359	-3.974359	15.795529	1.7600733
50	43.589744	6.4102564	41.091387	0.9426848
37	32.147436	4.8525641	23.547378	0.7324808
25	27.24359	-2.2435897	5.0336949	0.1847662
20	28.878205	-8.8782051	78.822526	2.7294815
38	38.141026	-0.1410256	0.0198882	0.0005214
10	17.179487	-7.1794872	51.545036	3.0003827
10	12.669872	-2.6698718	7.1282154	0.5626115
15	10.73718	4.2628205	18.171639	1.6924034
20	11.38141	8.6185897	74.280089	6.5264398

12	15.032051	-3.0320513	9.193335	0.6115822
2	5.1282051	-3.1282051	9.7856673	1.9082051
3	3.7820513	-0.7820513	0.6116042	0.1617123
3	3.2051282	-0.2051282	0.0420776	0.0131282
5	3.3974359	1.6025641	2.5682117	0.7559265
7	4.4871795	2.5128205	6.3142669	1.4071795
3	3.8461539	-0.8461539	0.7159763	0.1861539
2	2.8365385	-0.8365385	0.6997966	0.246708
2	2.4038462	-0.4038462	0.1630917	0.0678462
0	2.5480769	-2.5480769	6.492696	2.5480769
8	3.3653846	4.6346154	21.47966	6.3825275
Total			399.7628	35.18087

Chi-Square Test Formula:

$$X^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$$

O_i = Observed Frequency

E_i = Expected Frequency

Chi-Square Table:

Degree of Freedom = $(r-1)(c-1) = (5-1)(5-1) = (4)(4) = (16)$

Calculated Value = 35.18

For 16 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance, the chi-square table value is 26.296.

Interpretation:

Calculated value > Table value

Hence H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

Findings:

- 39 % of the respondents are 20 years Age.
- 71 % of the respondents are Male Genders.
- 46 % of respondents are yes in the like Continuous Assessment Practices.
- 26 % of respondents are Learning Process Understand by Continuous Assessment.
- 32 % of respondents are 3 Modes of Assignment in the one of the Best Continuous Assessment Practices.

Conclusion:

Therefore, the Continuous Assessment Practices should give more special attention in the college students by giving timely Assessment training to the students to conduct themselves better students , involving themselves in education and as well as quality of College Activities. Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur, is giving more importance in the Continuous Assessment Practices. This would definitely lead to a flourishing the best college.

References:

1. Kapambwe, M.W. (2010). The implementation of school based continuous assessment (CA) in Zambia.
2. Wiesemes, R. & Nickmans, G. (2006). A Learning Integrated Continuous Assessment System. Educational Research Review.
3. Quansah K.B (2005). Continuous assessment handbook (pp.2-3). Ghana education service publication. (BECAS).
4. Black, P. (2004). Redefining assessment the first ten years of “Continuous Assessment in Education”. Assessment in Education.
5. Boekaerts, M. (1999). Self-regulated learning: where we are today. International Journal of Educational Research.
6. Airasian, P.W. (1997). Classroom Assessment. (3rd Ed.). New York: McGraw- Hill Inc.
7. Arends, R. (1997). Class Room Instruction and Management. New York: McGraw-Hill Inc.